

Assessment of movement patterns in stroke patients: a case study with the Virtual Peg Insertion Test

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ABSTRACT

Abnormal movement patterns during upper-limb reaching tasks are often observed in patients after stroke, but clinical tools are lacking to objectively evaluate and quantify them. This paper presents the implementation and evaluation of six trajectory-based metrics on the Virtual Peg Insertion Test, a technology-based assessment of upper limb function consisting of a goal-directed peg-in-hole task. A case study with four stroke patients illustrates the ability of the proposed metrics to describe motion patterns that differ from age-matched healthy subjects, and thus to objectively assess and track abnormal movement patterns.

General Terms

Algorithms, Measurement, Performance, Experimentation.

Keywords

Abnormal synergies, upper limb, movement coordination, technology-based assessment.

1. INTRODUCTION

Stroke is the leading cause of long-term disability in adults, with more than half of stroke survivors suffering from arm and hand impairment, severely impacting their functional independence. Among a variety of upper limb impairments, abnormal movement patterns are typically observed in stroke patients. They can be seen as the functional consequence of arm muscle weakness and abnormal movement synergies, i.e. the inability to produce precise movements requiring the coordination of multiple joints [1, 2]. Although evaluating normal and abnormal synergies is an essential part of standard clinical assessments, such as the Fugl-Meyer motor Assessment Upper Extremity (FMA-UE) [3] these clinical scales lack sensitivity, are subjective and time-consuming to administer, and suffer from ceiling effects [4].

Technology-based assessments have the potential to offer more sensitive and objective metrics for the frequent evaluation of motor impairments in neurological patients [5]. They provide new means to evaluate patients during functional tasks, while

various types of sensors record movement trajectories, interaction forces/torques, or muscle activity. Several studies have used robotic devices to evaluate abnormal synergies of the upper extremity, by measuring the torque coupling between the different joints of the arm during movement [6, 7], the end-point force direction during reaching [8], or by analyzing arm kinematics during planar movement [2, 9]. These studies have proposed sensitive metrics to evaluate movement patterns of stroke patients and their changes over the course of rehabilitation. However, these tests typically require the execution of specific non-functional movements (e.g. circle drawing), or involve complex experimental setups (e.g. exoskeleton robot or optical tracking system).

The Virtual Peg Insertion Test (VPIT) is a simple assessment platform that can record and evaluate upper limb movements and grasping forces in the context of a functional, goal-directed task [10, 11]. Metrics descriptive of overall upper limb functional ability have been proposed and validated in stroke patients [12]. Nevertheless, the feasibility of detecting and characterizing abnormal movement patterns has not yet been systematically investigated. In this paper we propose the implementation of novel metrics, report case studies of four stroke patients exhibiting different representative movement patterns, and compare their performance to a group of age-matched healthy subjects.

2. METHODS

2.1 Virtual Peg Insertion Test

The Virtual Peg Insertion Test (VPIT, Figure 1A) is a technology-based upper limb assessment that combines a haptic device (PHANTOM Omni, Geomagic, USA) and a virtual environment displaying a pegboard task, similar to the conventional Nine Hole Peg Test [13]. During the assessment, pegs can be grasped, manipulated, and transported to holes in the virtual environment. This is achieved through the manipulation of a sphere of 5cm diameter, instrumented with force sensors, located at the output of the haptic device [11]. The endpoint position of the handle is represented in the virtual environment by a moving cursor that has to be precisely aligned with a peg. A grasping force above a threshold of 2N must be applied and maintained to pick up a peg and transport it to one of the holes. The proposed goal-directed task therefore involves fine position adjustments, control of grasping force, and upper limb coordination. The required movements to bring a peg to a hole correspond to a displacement of the handle of about 20cm, where the arm has to be moved away from the body, thus

Figure 1: A: Virtual Peg Insertion Test setup. B: Visual representation of a peg-to-hole trajectory projected onto the horizontal plane (blue line) and the ideal straight line between the peg's initial position and the selected hole (pink line). The proposed metrics to evaluate movement patterns include the maximum trajectory error (1), the minus trajectory metric (2) and the initial movement angle (4) (angle between the initial position and the position at the end of the initial phase of movement (3)).

requiring shoulder abduction and elbow extension, a typical movement against the commonly observed abnormal synergistic flexor pattern [1]. During the entire test, the haptic device renders interaction forces with the virtual pegboard and records three-dimensional trajectories, handle orientation and grasping forces at a rate of 1kHz for post processing and extraction of parameters representative of upper limb sensorimotor function. The feasibility of using the VPIT as objective assessment tool has been demonstrated in pilot studies with neurological patients [10, 11, 14].

2.2 Outcome measures and data analysis

In an assessment session, subjects perform five consecutive repetitions of the VPIT (i.e. inserting the nine pegs), preceded by a familiarization trial (not considered for data analysis). For the extraction of kinematic metrics, each repetition of the test is first divided into the nine trajectories corresponding to the handling of each peg. Each trajectory is then decomposed into approach phases (fine position adjustments around a peg, respectively hole) and gross movement phases using position and velocity thresholds (see [10] for details). Six metrics are selected to characterize upper limb movement patterns, considering the gross movement phases of the task only (go: peg to hole, return: hole to next peg). All data analyses are performed using Matlab R2014a (The MathWorks, USA).

The **Mean trajectory error (E_{traj})** represents the mean absolute error between the ideal straight line from peg to hole and the projection of the actual endpoint trajectory during a gross movement onto the horizontal plane. A large mean error can be indicative of compensatory movement (e.g. segmented movement with the arm moving close to the body), which can be the result of arm weakness or abnormal upper limb synergies.

The **Maximum absolute trajectory error (E_{max})** indicates how far the subject maximally deviates from the ideal straight line from peg to hole.

The **Minus trajectory metric (M)** measures the percentage of movement executed below (i.e. closer to the subject) the ideal straight line. A large minus trajectory metric (close to 1) together with a large E_{traj} might be indicative of typical compensatory movements [15].

The **Path length ratio (R_{PL})** is computed by dividing the length of the ideal straight line by the length of the actual path and has been reported to reflect movement efficiency [16] and overall upper limb coordination.

The **Trajectory smoothness (S_{traj})** can be used to evaluate movement coordination. Similar to movement smoothness parameters usually computed from derivatives of the velocity signals [14], this metric represents the number of maxima and minima in the error profile (number of zero-crossings of the error profile derivative). The error profile is computed as the difference between the straight line and the endpoint trajectory projected onto the horizontal plane.

The **Angle of initial movement (α_{aim})** can indicate the direction of the initial movement composing a gross movement phase. The end of the initial movement component is defined as the first speed minimum after the initial speed peak (i.e. first peak with a speed higher than 50% of the total maximum speed). The angle between the straight path and a direct line connecting to the end of initial movement is computed (Figure 1B, 3). A large angle will indicate that the subject did not properly aim towards the target and that the movement had to be slowed down and corrected [17].

For the data analysis, metrics were averaged over all trajectories and repetitions completed by each participant. In addition to the newly implemented trajectory metrics, the total time to execute a repetition of the test T_{ex} is also reported, as a measure of overall upper limb ability [14]. Results are reported as mean \pm std unless indicated otherwise. Differences between the individual performance of stroke patients and the mean performance of healthy subjects were considered significant if differences were larger than two standard deviations.

2.3 Participants

Data from four representative stroke patients were analyzed in the context of this study. Table 1 presents the demographic data of the stroke patients. For all four patients, FMA-UE scores were collected in parallel to the presented study. In addition, nine age-matched healthy subjects (65.8 ± 5.0 years old, 2 female and 7 male) were evaluated on the VPIT for reference data. All participants gave written informed consent prior to participation, and the study was approved by the ETH Zurich Ethics Commission.

3. RESULTS

Representative trajectories for the peg-to-hole movement of a healthy subject (H1) and two stroke patients (S1 and S2) are presented in Figure 2, and results of all metrics are reported in Table 2. Movements of healthy subjects tend to closely follow the optimal straight path resulting in small E_{traj} , E_{max} , S_{traj} and

Table 1. Stroke patient demographics.

	Gender	Age	FMA-UE ¹	TPS ²	TH ³
S1	F	69	58	6 months	D
S2	M	70	56	6 months	ND
S3	M	55	25	6 days	ND
S4	M	70	66	7 months	ND

¹Fugl-Meyer motor Assessment Upper Extremity, ²Time Post Stroke, ³Tested Hand (dominant D or nondominant ND).

α_{aim} , and a high R_{PL} . The total time to complete a repetition of the VPIT T_{ex} was significantly shorter than for all of the stroke patients.

The patterns of upper limb movement were found to vary widely in stroke patients. In S1, a high S_{traj} was observed (up to 16 times worse than for healthy subjects), while the trajectory error was not significantly different than the average of the healthy subjects, resulting in straight peg-to-hole movements (Figure 2). S2 exhibited an exceptionally large maximum error compared to healthy subjects (+160% for the go phase and +400% for the return phase) and to the other stroke patients. The minus metric M further indicates that a large percentage of these movements were executed in the region closer to the patient's body, resulting in curved trajectories (Figure 2). Additionally, R_{PL} is exceedingly small in comparison to the average healthy performance (-60% in the return phase) for this type of movement pattern. S3 also showed a small path length ratio, but only exhibiting a moderately large trajectory error. T_{ex} for patient S3 was found to be more than 10 times longer compared to a healthy subject and almost twice as long compared to the other stroke patients. S4 exhibited metrics that are closest to those of the healthy subjects. The trajectory error and the initial angle of movement are within the range, whereas the other metrics are only marginally worse than age-matched healthy subjects.

4. DISCUSSION

The objective of this paper was to implement kinematic metrics to evaluate upper limb movement patterns in stroke patients using the VPIT. The proposed metrics highlighted different behaviors in the four tested stroke patients. In particular, S1 exhibited straight movements (as indicated by a small E_{traj}), but with a high number of oscillations in the position profile, which could be indicative of a lack of coordination during multi-joint

upper limb movements [14]. In contrast, S2 performed smoother movements, but with large deviations from the straight line (E_{traj} and E_{max}), systematically moving the arm close to the body (high α_{aim}) and in a segmented fashion. This behavior was observed in all gross movement phases, but with larger errors in the return movements, where the movement is initiated with the arm in an extended position. This movement pattern is typical of the compensatory reaching strategies observed in stroke patients, and could be an indication of arm weakness and abnormal movement synergies [15]. Despite more pronounced upper limb impairment, S3, who was measured in the sub-acute phase after stroke, exhibited movement patterns similar to S1, but with a higher total execution time for the task. This was due to difficulties aligning the pegs with the holes at the end of gross movements (accounting for about 50% of T_{ex}), phases of the task that were not analyzed in detail in the present study focusing on gross movements. S4 performed the closest to age-matched healthy subjects, with small deviations from the ideal path, and the smallest S_{traj} metric. Note that S_{traj} is not time-normalized, which could partly explain the large differences observed between patients and healthy subjects. It should be noted that despite similarly mild upper-limb impairment (FMA-UE score >49), patients S1 and S2 showed very different movement patterns that are clearly different from healthy subjects. In addition, S4 is also exhibiting abnormal movement patterns despite reaching the maximum of 66 points on the FMA-UE score, illustrating the ceiling effect of the FMA-UE [4] and its limitations in providing detailed objective information on movement quality.

As could be expected from previous work [11, 12], all stroke patients required significantly more time to complete a repetition of the VPIT compared to healthy subjects, underlining the presence of upper limb sensorimotor deficits. All patients also had lower path length ratios, indicative of sub-efficient movement trajectories, in line with the results of other studies using similar metrics to evaluate movements of stroke patients [5]. Nevertheless, R_{PL} alone does not allow to fully describe the movement patterns used by a patient, underlining the need for combining more refined trajectory-based metrics to obtain a more complete picture of a patient's behavior. Future work will consist of validating the preliminary findings of this case study in a larger group of stroke patients, and simultaneously

Table 2. Trajectory metrics of nine healthy and four stroke subjects. Bold numbers represent values that differ from the average set by the healthy subjects by more than twice the std.

		Healthy (n=9)	S1	S2	S3	S4
E_{traj} [cm]	Go	0.42 ± 0.15	0.49 ± 0.06	0.91 ± 0.13	0.58 ± 0.01	0.57 ± 0.07
	Return	0.60 ± 0.18	0.84 ± 0.05	2.23 ± 0.36	0.71 ± 0.06	0.56 ± 0.08
E_{max} [cm]	Go	1.06 ± 0.41	1.30 ± 0.12	2.75 ± 0.61	1.57 ± 0.05	1.41 ± 0.18
	Return	1.34 ± 0.40	2.15 ± 0.13	6.30 ± 1.14	1.76 ± 0.22	1.21 ± 0.13
M [-]	Go	0.69 ± 0.18	0.68 ± 0.09	0.62 ± 0.10	0.68 ± 0.04	0.59 ± 0.03
	Return	0.81 ± 0.10	0.89 ± 0.05	0.94 ± 0.01	0.64 ± 0.13	0.67 ± 0.01
R_{PL} [-]	Go	0.89 ± 0.03	0.61 ± 0.08	0.58 ± 0.10	0.62 ± 0.03	0.78 ± 0.04
	Return	0.83 ± 0.03	0.50 ± 0.08	0.34 ± 0.03	0.45 ± 0.03	0.69 ± 0.03
S_{traj} [-]	Go	5.93 ± 1.54	61.91 ± 17.80	25.48 ± 7.80	37.79 ± 6.08	17.59 ± 7.12
	Return	4.21 ± 1.01	67.66 ± 11.58	26.63 ± 5.88	45.37 ± 15.20	29.03 ± 10.78
α_{aim} [°]	Go	3.55 ± 1.83	10.91 ± 1.73	19.69 ± 5.41	16.51 ± 3.73	6.95 ± 0.97
T_{ex} [s]	Total	39.37 ± 11.49	288.54 ± 16.01	229.22 ± 25.28	424.36 ± 52.34	157.57 ± 39.15

Figure 2: Example of three representative trajectories and computed metrics for a hole-to-peg (return) movement for a healthy subject (H1) and two stroke patients (S1 and S2).

collecting clinical and neurophysiological data that could shed light on the expected link between the proposed metrics and upper limb impairment, in particular arm weakness and pathological synergies.

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